

Enhancing Low-Inertia Power Systems with Grid Forming Based Hybrid Energy Storage Technology

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Abstract— This paper delves into the significance of integrating Hybrid Energy Storage Systems (UCAP and Battery) equipped with Grid-Forming (GFM) conversion in low-inertia systems. Considering recent advancements in power system dynamics and control strategies, the study emphasizes the crucial role of hybrid energy system from the DC side of the grid forming converter in addressing the challenges posed by reduced system inertia on grid stability. Through an in-depth analysis of system inertia dynamics and frequency control mechanisms, the paper elucidates how HESS-GFM systems can emulate synchronous generators, thereby covering wide range of services like conventional generators. The aim of this paper is mainly on exploring the operational advantages of using a hybrid system in comparison to the BESS system considering aspects such as frequency regulation, and grid resynchronization stability. The findings underscore the importance for utilities, policymakers, and researchers to prioritize the deployment and optimization of hybrid energy storage technologies for GFM conversion systems as fundamental strategies for ensuring future grid stability and advancing the transition toward a sustainable energy landscape.

Keywords—*Hybrid energy storage, Energy integration, Grid forming converter, Low inertia systems, Power system control.*

I. INTRODUCTION

In the pursuit of decarbonizing electricity generation, a notable surge in the adoption of renewable energy technologies, particularly solar and wind power, has been witnessed [1]-[2]. Commonly, these renewable sources interface with the grid through converters necessitating a conversion-based generation unit, commonly referred to as Grid Following (GFL), to facilitate power injection from the plant level. These types of converters synchronize their output to the grid frequency and voltage. GFL converters follow the grid's frequency and voltage, adjusting their output accordingly to inject power into the grid. Consequently, the deployment of renewable energy parks has gradually displaced traditional synchronous generator-based thermal generation and this growth initiates the need for a more advanced control system [3]-[4].

The escalating penetration of renewable generation has exposed a vulnerability in the network, leading to technical constraints on the maximum penetration of renewable generation reliant on GFL converters. Unlike traditional synchronous generators, renewable energy sources connected through GFL converters do not inherently contribute to grid inertia, which is crucial for maintaining system stability during transient events such as sudden load changes or disturbances. This bottleneck can be mitigated by the integration of Grid Forming (GFM) converters, also known as grid formers.

In recent years, numerous reports have emerged that focus on developing control algorithms mimicking the behavior of synchronous generators [5] to mitigate this loss in inertial support. Over the past decade, virtual synchronous machines have garnered considerable attention [6]. Various methods have employed direct voltage control techniques aimed at replicating the electromotive force of the generator [7]-[9]. Unlike GFL converters that simply follow the grid, GFM converters have the capability to establish and control the grid's voltage and frequency autonomously. By assuming grid-forming capabilities, these converters can provide essential inertia and stability support to the grid, even in the absence of synchronous generators.

Despite the feasibility and functionality of grid-forming controls, the real industrial application demands wide range of services. This needs from these GFM converters often necessitate auxiliary energy storage, typically high-power type storages connected to the DC side of the conversion system. While the integration of GFM converters represents a significant advancement in enhancing grid stability, their effectiveness in mitigating grid challenges can be further augmented by incorporating hybrid energy storage systems. Storage systems connected to the DC side of converters play a crucial role in enhancing the converter's capabilities and providing additional grid services [10].

One of the primary functions of storage in conjunction with GFM converters is to provide fast-acting power support during transient events. Energy storage systems, such as batteries and ultra-capacitors, can respond rapidly to fluctuations in grid conditions, helping to stabilize frequency and voltage deviations. Additionally, storage systems enable GFM converters to deliver ancillary grid services such as frequency regulation, voltage support, and grid resilience. But in order to meet the requirements of the future power grid, a single storage technology is not recommendable. Transmission System Operators (TSO's) are realizing that many of the problems to be addressed in modern distributed generation scenarios should have a "power characteristic", enabling a fast response to provide different services like frequency regulation, fast peak shaving, virtual inertia, or power smoothing, which cannot be provided sufficiently in low-inertia systems with a high share of renewable based energy systems. This "pain point", which creates uncertainties about performance and degradation, is currently being addressed by oversizing a (Battery Energy Storage System) BESS solution (only battery-based system), which entails additional costs (in CAPEX and OPEX) in an expensive technology (usually Li-Ion) and eliminates the cost effectiveness of the BESS solution. It is worth mentioning that sizing based on power requirements with non-optimal technology implies oversizing in terms of power [2].

To solve this “pain point”, a hybrid approach based on decoupling power and energy and satisfying both needs with the combination of energy storage technologies with characteristics that adjust to the needs of each specific scenario, avoiding oversizing and excessive degradation by using technology outside of its control area is proposed. For such study batteries can provide energy-based services while the UCAP’s can offer high power density with fast response services, preventing excessive degradation and oversizing of batteries. In general, energy storage systems offer the flexibility to store surplus energy during periods of low demand and discharge it during peak demand, thereby optimizing grid operations and enhancing overall system efficiency. By integrating storage on the DC side of GFM converters, grid operators can leverage the combined capabilities of storage and grid-forming technology to address grid stability challenges and facilitate the seamless integration of renewable energy sources into the grid.

This paper is dedicated to elucidating our recent endeavors in implementing and experimenting with grid forming systems augmented by hybrid energy storage solutions (HES), as undertaken across various projects in collaboration with the Spanish Transmission System Operator (TSO) such as *RES+* project [10]. With a focus on showcasing practical experiences, we delve into the pivotal role of grid formers and HESs in bolstering grid stability and resilience. By highlighting key aspects of grid formers and HES systems, we aim to underscore their efficacy in providing an array of essential services to the grid such as island operation and frequency regulation in grid connected mode of operation. Through comprehensive analysis and empirical findings, we illuminate the multifaceted contributions of these technologies in facilitating seamless integration of renewable energy sources and ensuring the reliability and sustainability of the grid infrastructure.

II. STUDIED SYSTEM

The studied scenario is a weak network in connection with a 2.5 MW grid forming-based conversion system. The schematic of this system is presented in Fig. 1. It is composed of an equivalent generator as the external grid, Battery and UCAP, local loads, AC/DC power converters and transformers. In this test benchmark, the external grid is modelled by an equivalent generation unit consisting of equivalent inertia (H_{eq}) and damping for such a grid. A local load is also added for generating different events to the systems. The rating and generic technical data of the developed system can be found in Table 1.

TABLE 1. SYSTEM DATA.

External grid equivalent	Ex. Loads	Local Load	Cable (Lg)
Rating: 100 MVA 12 kV, Inertia: 3 s	P= 30 MW Q= 6MVAR	P=1.62 MW Q=0 MVAR	Length: 0,5 km R = 0,125 Ω /km, X_L = 0,106 Ω /km C = 0,306 μ F/km

As shown in Fig. 1, there are different energy management systems called InMS. The InMS® (Intelligent Node Management System), also known as Energy Management System (EMS), is a hardware and software control platform that integrates algorithms, aimed at optimal planning and multi-service operation by the end user based on a deep understanding of storage technologies and their performance in real applications at network scale.

The InMS optimally monitors and manages the flow of energy in the storage system and can also function as a micro grid controller. The InMS® manages the BMS work of the batteries or other storage assets (such as the ultracapacitor controller), and various system components. In addition, the EMS can also function as a SCADA system, collecting and processing data for real-time decision-making, real-time analysis, and data archiving for future analysis. As shown in this figure, two versions of InMS control are used in this study. One is called InMS-SHAD, which will carry out the control and parametrization of the power electronics linked to HESS system, together with the rapid response services, using the rapid acquisition of signals from the DC bus. On the other hand, at a higher level there will be another InMS-uGRID which will perform the microgrid management, SCADA supervision and connection to other electrical assets.

Figure 1. General simulation scenario with an equivalent external network.

III. HIERARCHICAL CONTROL STRUCTURE

The general hierarchical control structure for performing the different control levels for a grid-forming (GFM) power electronic based generation units is presented in Fig. 2. For flexible and high-level controls an Intelligent Node Management System (InMS) is designed and used for validating the HESS GFM system capabilities. Modbus over TCP is used for its communication. Modbus TCP is the standard communication protocol used in this study for the InMS equipment to control other devices and to communicate with other systems such as SCADA supervision.

Figure 2. General control structure of the GFM power converter-based unit for dynamic studies.

As shown in Fig. 2, the first control level (CTRL1) consists of the inner current controller, power electronic level, which can give the modulated voltage signals to the converter. The second control level (CTRL2) is mainly related to the outer loop controllers and grid functionalities, which is giving proper input signal to CTRL1. Additional grid functionalities can be utilized as part of CTRL2 and CTRL3 outer loop controls such as Virtual inertia and Frequency control or POD.

The core of the grid forming action is presented in Fig. 3 which is located at the CTRL2 level for managing the voltage and angle. In this project, the DC side is shared between battery and UCAP in a way that fast response actions can be covered by UCAP and the rest by Battery. By mixing these two technologies, in the scheme of a hybrid solution, we can provide different types of services like fast peak shaving, simultaneous virtual inertia, frequency control and power-oscillation damping (POD). The third and fourth control levels (CTRL3 and CTRL4) are mainly related to additional tasks or coordination and virtualization of components. Fig. 3 shows the supplementary control loops used: VSM control (synchronous generator emulation) with electromechanical characteristics and reactive power/voltage droop control.

Figure 3. Outer control loop at the CTRL2 level.

The self-synchronization mechanism, shown in Fig. 3, allows the converter to operate in synchronism with an external grid. There are different variants of self-synchronization mechanisms, such as power-frequency droop control (P-f) or virtual synchronous machine control [4]. This mechanism results in a reference angle output, which will be an input to CTRL2.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

In this section, the developed GFM control concept is tested with the equivalent grid shown in Fig. 1. The used data for this test are presented in Table 1. While for having a better contribution to the SCR of the used small system, a smaller virtual admittance has been selected. The goal of this test is to check the following capabilities:

- Startup of the converter and work in Island mode
- Island mode support-load change and resynchronization
- Switch from island to grid connected operating mode.

Therefore, the simulation is managed to have the initialization part in PSCAD and then checking the starting up the HESS converter in island mode. Then simulation is performed to show the grid forming operation of HESS, testing its capability on

feeding the local loads and its synchronization with the main external grid. The used wind power profiles for this scenario are shown in Figs 4 and 5.

The evolution of active and reactive power output of HESS system with the GFM control are presented in Figs 5 and 6. According to the results shown in these figures, the HESS GFM system and wind model was able to pass the initialization part of the PSCAD with successful startup in island mode. As one can see the GFM converter system was able to form the grid by feeding the remaining local load, around 500 kW. In order to test the capability of the GFM converter on feeding the local load in island mode, at 6 sec there was a load step increase in island around 120 kW.

The converter was able to automatically increase its output power for feeding the local loads. Resynchronization occurs at $t=16$ sec. Automatic switching of the GFM converter system happens around 16 sec of the simulation time which shows the successful operation of the synchronization logic of the system. After switching to grid connected mode, the converter is changing its active power output as the power setpoint requested for grid connected mode operation (in this case was set to 1 MW) while during island mode operation it was only feeding the local loads.

This issue will be the same for reactive power support as it can be seen in Figure 5, in island mode GFM supported some reactive power for local load while after grid connected mode around 16 sec, is moved to zero reactive power setpoint.

Figure 4. Active and reactive power curves of Wind Park.

Figure 5. Active power of HESS converter system.

- a) initialization and load step change at 6 sec in island mode,
- b) synchronization action and switch from island to grid connected mode.

Figure 6. Reactive power of HESS converter system. (at 16 sec is switched from island to grid connected mode).

This smooth reaction of HESS converter system is due to the hybridized energy support from the DC side consisting of both UCAP and battery technologies. The contribution of hybrid system as output power from UCAP and battery is shown in Fig. 7. As can be observed all the fast reactions are compensated by UCAP while the role of battery is to support the recovery for long term action for a hybrid solution. These fast reactions from UCAP are happening at $t=6$ sec, when a local step load change happened, and at 16 sec, when after synchronization switching from island to grid connected mode happened. For responding the increase in local load, the output power of UCAP increased while for switching to grid connected mode the UCAP was absorbing the surplus power to let the converter to follow the requested set point in grid connected mode. The shape of SOC for BESS and UCAP in HESS systems are also presented in Figs 8 and 9. These figures show the evolution of UCAP for absorbing a huge amount of power in a very short period compared to battery technologies. As shown in these figures, for switching from island to grid connected mode, in less than 10 s almost 10% of the SOC is used by UCAP, which is much faster than the battery.

Figure 7. Output power comparison of storage technologies. a) overall response, b) Zoom during resynchronization and connection to the grid.

Figure 8. SOC of Battery system.

Figure 9. SOC of UCAP component.

Thanks to the fast reactions from UCAPs, it can be understood that the level of stress can be reduced significantly during the operation of batteries, which can decrease the battery sizing (CAPEX), provide a reduction in operation and maintenance costs of the batteries (OPEX), and increasing the synergy with other grid services enhancing economic profitability (such as Time Shifting or Arbitrage).

V. CONCLUSIONS

According to the performed analysis in the PSCAD simulation, the following outcomes can be highlighted:

- A grid forming (FGM) hybrid system is presented and analyzed with the main capability of forming the grid in island mode and automatic switching between island and grid connected mode of operations.
- A synchronizer logic is added and assessed to help the action of islanding and reconnection of the HESS. In this case, monitoring with fast communication technology will be important.
- Having both batteries and UCAP, Hybrid solution, can bring more flexibilities with improving the dynamic stability of the system.
- Including UCAP, at an optimal sizing, will be necessary to release the stress on the batteries, especially for short term services.
- Proper tuning of the GFM controller will be important to guarantee an acceptable overall dynamic performance.
- Thanks to the hybridization, the batteries are not going to react continuously. This is important since continuous operation would have a very negative impact on the acceleration of battery degradation. However, with a HESS system, it could be continuously regulated as it would be the UCAP's who attend to the high frequency events, preventing the power battery from continuously implementing the regulation. Therefore, the response of the service would be improved and a reduction in the degradation of the power battery is also achievable.
- Based on the results, the GFM HESS system is capable of synchronization and forming the grid in island mode while in island mode it can feed the local load even with step changes and in grid connected mode can provide regular regulation services against any type of load step changes.

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